

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DISON I. ACEBUCHE, LPT, MACDDS

College Instructor

COLEGIO DE SANTA RITA DE SAN CARLOS, INC.

San Carlos City, Negros Occidental

dison.acebuche@gmail.com

“The Maiden by the Acacia Tree”

On grassy height where flowers open wide,
Fair blooms dance to the whispering air,
A maiden sits, her beauty to abide,
With daffodil in hand, she sings with care.

She salutes the butterflies and the birds in flight,
The grasses bend, the ants stop at her song—
Her voice so pure, enralls the morning light,
As nature joins her gentle, sweet prolong.

Her ruby lips, like macopa, so bright
With golden tresses flowing, soft and free—
Her eyes, twin stars that sparkle in the night—
No earthly charm compares to such as she.

She holds my heart within her tender snare,
In love’s pure paradise, I’d linger there.

PACIFICUS EDITORIAL TEAM

Managing Editor: Roger B. Rueda, PhD

Managing Director: Kevin F. Suaganog, MED

Proprietor/Head Designer: Bryan G. Gamarcha

New Poblacion, Buenavista, Guimaras